

CO-OPERATIVE LEARNING STRATEGIES AND ITS ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL SKILLS AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN B. ED STUDENTS

Wadhe Pritesh Rama

Ph.D Research scholar

Department of Education

Shri Jagdishprasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University, Jhunjhunu, Rajasthan

Dr. Jadhav Keshar Ramchandra

Assistant Professor

Abstract

Education is a foundation stone of nation's intellectual power which shapes the power profile of a nation in the community of world nations, thus, it is rightly said that the progress of a country particularly of a democratic country depends upon the quality of teachers. Teacher education plays an important role not only in development of teaching skills, pedagogical knowledge but also it could play a leading role in the development of professional skills and emotional intelligence among B. Ed students. Co-operative learning is an educational approach that aims to organize classroom activities in to academic and social learning experiences. It is very important for B. Ed students to understand the kind of professional skills they required in this profession and how to develop them by learning co-operatively. It is also important for B. Ed students to understand the concept of emotional intelligence, different factors of emotional intelligence and its importance in their teaching profession Co-operative learning can be one of the options to develop the professional skills and emotional intelligence in secondary teacher trainees

Keywords: *Co-operative learning strategies, Professional skills, Emotional Intelligence, B. Ed students*

Introduction:

Education is the foundation stone of nation's intellectual power which shapes the power profile of a nation in the community of world nations, thus, it is rightly said that the progress of a country particularly of a democratic country depends up on the quality of teachers. Teacher education plays an important role not only in

development of teaching skills, pedagogical knowledge but also it could play a leading role in the development of professional skills and emotional intelligence among B. Ed students. Kothari commission (1964) stated that “Nothing is more important than securing a sufficient supply of high quality of recruits of the teaching profession providing them with the best possible profession preparation and creating satisfactory conditions of work in which they can be fully effective” Teacher training education plays an important role to develop good quality teachers for the country. Teaching information, techniques and methods are constantly being updated and changed. Teacher centered learning is not sufficient to fulfill the requirement of education hence there is a need of strategies based on the student centered approach.

Teacher Education:

Teacher education refers to the policies and procedures designed to equip prospective teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviors and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the classroom, school and wider community. In more clear word teacher education means logical arrangement of various components like subject content, methodologies of teachings, skills and values to prepare teachers with right attitude, efficiency and effectiveness.

Stages of structure of Teacher Education in India:

1. Teacher education at pre-primary level for pre-primary school level called as Early Childhoods Care Education (E.C.C.Ed)
2. Teacher education at primary level for primary school level called as Diploma in Elementary Education (D.El.Ed)
3. Teacher education at secondary level for secondary and higher secondary school level called as Bachelor in Education (B.Ed)
4. Teacher education at Tertiary level called as Master in Education (M..Ed)
5. Teacher education at quaternary level based on research called M.Phil and Ph.D

Among the all levels of education, secondary level of teacher education plays an important role in an individual's life as it act a bridge between primary and higher secondary level of education. This period is considered very important because at this stage, students learn to acquire various values and skills like life skills, social skills which lead to overall development of his personality.

Co-operative Learning:

Co-operative learning strategies are based on social constructivism which is one of the main streams of constructivism. In this concept, students work in a small group and collectively for better learning. Students get the chance for the active participation than the passive listener like in traditional teaching methods. Co-operative learning is an educational approach that aims to organize classroom activities in to academic and social learning experiences. In cooperative learning students needs to work in groups to complete the given task collectively towards academic goals. Unlike individual learning, which can be competitive in nature, students work in a cooperation to acquire knowledge and to develop certain skills and everyone succeeds when group succeeds In 1994, Johnson and Johnson published the 5 elements i.e. Positive interdependence, Individual accountability, Face to Face interaction, Social skills and group processing essential for effective group achievement, effective group learning and higher order social, personal and cognitive skills (e.g. Problem solving, Decision making, Reasoning, Planning, Organizing and reflecting)

Elements of Cooperative learning:

1. Positive interdependence:

Group members are obliged to rely on one another to achieve the common goal. Students must fully participate and put forth effort within their group.

2. Individual accountability:

All students in a group are held accountable for doing their share of work and for mastery of all of the material to be learned.

3. Face to face promotive interaction:

Group members promote each other's success. Students explain to one another what they are learning and assist one another in completion of task by providing feedback, challenging reasoning and conclusions.

4. Social Skills:

Social skills development is a part of cooperative learning. Skills include effective communication, Interpersonal and group skills

1. Communication
2. Leadership
3. Trust-building
4. Friendship development
5. Decision -making
6. Conflict Management skill

5. Group processing:

Group members set group goals, assess regularly what they are doing well as a group and identify changes they will make to function more effectively in the future.

Types of Cooperative learning:

1. Formal cooperative learning

Formal cooperative learning is more structured, facilitated, monitored by educator and it is used to achieve group goals in task work e.g. completing a unit

2. Informal cooperative learning

Informal cooperative learning incorporates group learning with passive teaching by drawing attention to material through small group by discussion at the ends of lesson e.g. Turn to your partner discussion

3. Base group learning:

It is effective for learning complex subject matter over the course of semester e.g. Long term study group.

Cooperative learning strategies:

There are a great number of cooperative learning strategies. Some cooperative learning strategies utilize students pairing, while other utilize small group of four and more students. Hundreds of techniques have been practiced to use in content area of subject.

Following cooperative learning strategies are widely used in teaching learning process.

1. Think Pair share
2. Jigsaw
3. Jigsaw II
4. Reverse Jigsaw
5. Reciprocal Teaching
6. Problem Based Learning (PBL)
7. Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD)
8. Team Game Tournament (TGT)

Advantages and applicability of cooperative learning strategies:

1. Cooperative learning strategies are usually equally effective for all ability level.
2. Students demonstrate academic achievement.
3. Cooperative learning strategies helps to develop certain skills in students.
4. Cooperative learning strategies are effective for all ethnic groups.
5. Student's perceptions of one another are enhanced.
6. Cooperative learning strategies increases self esteem and self concept.
7. Cooperative learning strategies leads to higher level reasoning.
8. Cooperative learning strategies leads to new ideas and solutions.
9. Cooperative learning strategies leads to greater transfer of learning between situations

Professional skills:

The phrase "Professional skills" is used in the broad sense to describe skills that

complement the disciplinary knowledge and disciplinary technical skills that remain the most important aspect of any graduate training (Canadian Association of Graduate Studies). Professional skills are skills simply referred to the skills necessary for graduate to succeed in his professional practice. Pre-service teacher education programme aim to prepare to prepare graduate to become quality teachers equipped with pedagogical practices that will serve to meet the increasing demand associated with the teaching profession.(Bransford, Darling-Hammord &Lepage,2005)

Today's teachers have many challenges. The rise in technology, privatization of education, low salary and social expectations has transformed teaching profession, nevertheless. A teacher must have contained certain skills to navigate through the journey of modern education. Teaching profession is one of the noble professions. A teacher should acquire necessary professional skills and ethics related to this profession to deal with the challenges and opportunities and challenges related to this profession. "Professional skills of teacher are categories of skills which are required to a trained teacher to succeed in his teaching professional practices"

It is important to teach professional skills to teachers right from their pre-service training period but only core teaching skills are encouraged during last few decades.

Need of Professional skills to teachers:

Newly trained teachers entering in teaching job first time face number of problems and challenges especially how to learn and function in an unpredictable and unfamiliar situations in new school environment. B. Ed students should recognize the importance of professional skills for early and subsequent career advancements.

Co-operative learning and Professional skills:

There may be a direct relationship between cooperative learning and professional skills required in the teaching profession. Today's world is a world of globalization

and modernization. Every sector is in the race of success and development. Education sector is also grooving and mostly depends upon the qualities of the teachers. Cooperative learning could help the teacher training students to develop the professional skills to cope up with the worst situations and incoming challenges. If teachers all round development starts during their training period, it would help the students to develop their personality and help them in their future careers.

Emotional Intelligence:

Emotional intelligence can best be described as the ability to monitor one's own and other people's emotions, to discriminate between different emotions and label them appropriately, and to use emotional information to guide thinking and behavior. In other words Emotional Intelligence (EI) refers to an ability to perceive, control and evaluate emotions.

Studies have shown that people having high EI shows greater mental health, job performance and potent leadership.

Emotional Intelligence (EI) is supported by 3 models

1. Ability model developed by Peter Salovey and John Mayer.
2. Trait model developed by Konstanin Vasily Petrides
3. Mixed model by Daniel Goleman

Goleman in 1998 adapted Solvey and Mayers (1990) model for his discussion of the theory of emotional intelligence and its implication on everyday life. He developed five emotional and social competencies of emotional intelligence.

1. Self awareness:

The ability to recognize and understand one's own mood and emotions and drives as well as their effects on others.

2. Self regulation:

The ability to control or redirect disruptive impulses and mood. The propensity to suspend judgment- to think before acting.

3. Motivation:

A passion to work for reasons that go beyond money or status. A propensity to pursue goals with energy and persistence.

4. Empathy:

The ability to understand the emotional make up of other people. Skills in treating people according to their emotional reactions.

5. Social skills:

Proficiency in managing relationship and building networks. An ability to find common ground and build rapport.

Importance of Emotional Intelligence for B. Ed students:

Research showed that academically successful people had high level of emotional competencies. For helping students to acquire the skills of emotional competencies, in the first phase teacher need to be trained in the emotional intelligence to manage their own emotions and those of others. Emotionally intelligent teacher can serve as an important role model for students.

Co-operative learning and Emotional Intelligence:

Right from the ancient education system more stress was given on the cognitive development of the students and emotional development has been totally ignored as our curriculum is mainly based on intellectual development of the child. Hence it is a need of today to strengthen the emotional intelligence of the students and it would be possible if we introduce new strategies of cooperative learning in the curriculum. The success of teaching is depends upon the required professional skills. Cooperative learning can help the teacher training students to improve their professional skills.

Conclusion:

Teaching of professional skills through a teacher centered learning is not that much useful to B. Ed students. Co-operative learning strategies would be the best way to learn them properly. Learning and practicing of cooperative learning strategies

would help B. Ed students to get some benefits like achievements, retention, improvements in relations, improved critical thinking skills, oral communication improvement, promoted social skills, heightened self esteem. B. Ed course is generally taught by using lecture method which is not 100% useful to develop necessary professional skills in students hence it is very important to teach the syllabus by using co-operative learning strategies.

References:

Aggarwal J.C. (2008) “Educational Reforms in India” for the 21st century, *Shipra Publication, New Delhi.*

Cohen, B.P. & Cohen, E.G. (1991). From groupwork among children to R & D teams: interdependence, interaction and productivity, *In Lawler, E.J.,*

Goleman, D. (1998). *Working with emotional intelligence.* Bantam.

Johnson, D.W. & Johnson, R.T. (1989) Cooperation and Competition Theory and Research. *Edina, Minnesota; USA. Interaction Book Co. publishing.*

Marjan Laal, Seyed Mohammad Ghodsi (2012) “Benefits of collaborative learning” *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences 31 (2012) 486 – 490*

Salovey, P. & Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional intelligence. *Imagination, Cognition, and Personality, 9, 185-211*

Sharma S.P (2016) *Teacher Education: Principles, Theories and Practice,* Kanishka Publishers, Distributors, New Delhi.

(www.wikipedia.org/wiki/Teacher_education)

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4085815>